

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BATUMA****FIRST NAME: DEAN****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MSWord-Office 365 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What does the "ethics of science" require when I use words, charts, graphs, or data from work belonging to someone else in my work?
- Identify what you borrowed by citing sources.¹**
 - Please use it without permission.
 - Recognize the author only when the author dies.
 - Acknowledge the author only if the author is well known.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 321.

2. According to Adu (2016), which of the following statements is not considered one of the main components of Chapter 3 in qualitative research?
- Research question and research design.
 - Procedures, data processing, and quality assurance.
 - Population, Participants, and Sampling Method.
 - Results and Findings.**²
3. What is Plagiarism?
- Using the source without naming the creator of the original.
 - Copy and paste the entire text without acknowledging the author of this source.
 - Paraphrasing without proper citation.
 - All of the above.**³
4. Choose the correct format for structuring an essay?
- The introduction moves from general to specific, the body concerns paragraphs (each paragraph is a building block of your argument), and the conclusion moves from particular to general.**⁴

² Philip Adu, "Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study" (The Chicago School of Professional Psychology, 2016), 6:25, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, vol. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 10.

- The introduction moves from the specific to the general; the body consists of paragraphs (each a building block of your argument), and the conclusion from the particular to the general.
 - The introduction moves from general to specific, the body consists of paragraphs (each a building block of your argument), and the conclusion goes from introduction to specific.
 - The opening moves from specific to general, the body consists of paragraphs (each a building block of your argument), and the conclusion goes from a general idea to a particular one.
5. According to Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021), which style guide does EUCLID University recommend for academic writing?
- MLAs.
 - APA
 - Harvard.
 - Chicago (Turabian), but other internationally accepted rules are acceptable.⁵**
6. Which of the following statements best describes the purpose of chapter 3 of the research paper?
- Providing a summary of the literature review.
 - Publication of research results and findings.

⁵ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 41.

- Understand the methodological implications of decisions and encourage readers to think carefully about the relationship between research goals, research questions, approaches, and methods.⁶**
- Discuss the limitations of the research.
7. Which of the following questions is not one of the research questions researchers should ask, as described by Bloomberg and Dale (2019)?
- What does this problem or issue mean to me personally or professionally?⁷**
- Is my research question socially and culturally important? Why? How?
- Will this study expand my knowledge base on my expertise?
- What is the estimated timeframe for completing this research project before applying for a position?
8. What is the purpose of the citations in square brackets in the Turabian (2018) author-date style citations?
- To provide additional comments or clarifications about the source.⁸**
- Indicate the page number of the cited source.
- Provide complete bibliographic information about the source.
- Provide a summary or synopsis of the original.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 435.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 324.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 141.

9. What is the primary purpose of preparing the literature review by Bloomberg and Volpe (2019)?

- Determine the accomplishments in the field and place the subject within the existing framework.⁹**
- Identify gaps and flaws in existing research.
- To demonstrate extensive knowledge of the issue
- Provide a detailed summary of all sources on the topic.

10. Which of the following statements best describes the difference between practical and conceptual problems in research?

- Practical questions are about what to do, and conceptual questions focus on what to think.¹⁰**
- Practical problems are most common in academia, while conceptual issues are most common in the professional world.
- Both empirical and conceptual problems are equally common in the scientific and professional worlds.
- The conceptual problem is what to do, and the practical problem is what to think.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 14.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 29.

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